

Annex to: Scientific opinion on the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen and defrosting of frozen ungulates meat. doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2026.9825

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Annex A – Protocol for the assessment of the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen and on defrosting of frozen ungulates meat

A.1 Introduction

A.1.1 Scope of this protocol

This annex outlines the protocol for the scientific assessments to be conducted for the request for two scientific opinions from the EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards (BIOHAZ): one on the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen, and another on the microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates: defrosting.

This protocol was developed with the aim of defining the methods for data collection, appraising the relevant evidence, and analysing and integrating the evidence in light of the identified uncertainties. It was developed following the principles and process defined in a project that aimed to further improve EFSA's scientific assessment processes (EFSA, 2015) and based on the recommendations for protocol development described in the Guidance on protocol development for EFSA generic scientific assessments (EFSA SC, 2023).

After establishing the objectives of the assessment, including clarification and interpretation of the Terms of Reference (TOR) received (section A.1.2. and A.1.3), both steps in the protocol development are described, starting with the formulation of the problem (section A.2) followed by the planning of the methods for conducting the assessment (section A.3).

The protocol was drafted by the WG members and was approved by the BIOHAZ Panel at their 176th plenary meeting (12-13 March 2025).

A.1.2 Background and Terms of Reference (ToR) as provided by the requestor

A.1.2.1 Request for a scientific opinion on the microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates intended to be frozen

Regulation (EC) No 853/2004¹ lays down a limited number of specific requirements for the hygiene of frozen meat of ungulates:

- Some information requirements (date of production and date of freezing) are laid down in Section IV of Annex II;
- Fresh meat of ungulates intended to be frozen must be frozen after slaughter without undue delay taking into account, where necessary, a stabilisation period before freezing in accordance with point 4 of Chapter VII in Section I (domestic ungulates) and point 1 of Section III (even-toed farmed game) to Annex III.

¹ Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 laying down specific hygiene rules for food of animal origin (OJ L 139, 30.4.2004, p. 55)

Additional EU harmonized requirements on the storage and transport temperatures of certain frozen food exist:

- Council Directive 89/108/EEC² includes, among others, a maximum temperature of -18°C for storage and transport of quick-frozen food. The percentage of quick-frozen meat of ungulates placed on the market is low compared to frozen meat of such animals;
- For minced meat, meat preparations, mechanically separated meat and fishery products, a maximum temperature for storage and transport of frozen products is laid down in Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 (-18°C, respectively in Annex III, Section V, Point 2(c)(ii) and 4(f), and Section VIII, Chapter I(C)(1) and Chapter III(B) with the exception of whole fish frozen in brine intended for canning: not more than -9°C, Chapter II(7)).

No maximum temperature limits for the storage and transport are laid down and wordings such as "undue delay" and "stabilisation" or "stabilisation period" are not defined. There is no scientific opinion developed by EFSA or the former Scientific Committees of the Commission providing recommendations to lay down possible additional EU harmonized requirements on frozen meat.

In points 2.1.1 to 2.1.4 of Chapter 2 of Annex I to Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005³, some process hygiene criteria (aerobic colony count, Enterobacteriaceae, *Salmonella*) have been laid down for carcasses of ungulates after dressing but before chilling in slaughterhouses. After that stage, some additional process hygiene criteria (aerobic colony count) are only laid down for (fresh) carcasses in specific transport situations in accordance with point (3)(b)(viii) in Chapter VII of Section I of Annex III to Regulation (EC) No 853/2004.

Recently, the Commission updated its staff working document: "*Guidance on the implementation of certain provisions of Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 on the hygiene of food of animal origin*"⁴, among others by adding a Section 5.8. This section provides the Commission interpretation on freezing of fresh meat without undue delay, mainly from a legal perspective by lack of scientific data on the risk. The Commission also recently amended the requirements of Regulation (EC) No 853/2004, providing a derogation on the obligation to freeze meat without undue delay, in case of dry-ageing of beef⁵, allowing freezing of dry-aged bovine meat until 35 days from the end of the stabilisation period upon slaughter).

From a risk point of view, some inconsistency exists within Regulation (EC) No 853/2004. The Regulation allows for the preparation of minced meat, followed by freezing, from chilled meat within no more than 15 days from the slaughter of the animals in case of boned vacuum-packed beef and veal (Point 2(b) and (c) in Chapter III of Section V of Annex III to Regulation 853/2004). Freezing of the same vacuum-packed meat without mincing, is not allowed, although this seems to be a safer practice since mincing may represent an increased risk of microbiological growth of the product.

The above illustrates the need for a scientific opinion to provide a risk-based justification of existing or a scientific basis for possible amendments to these EU requirements for the freezing of meat to guarantee the microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates.

² Council Directive 89/108/EEC of 21 December 1988 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to quick-frozen foodstuffs for human consumption (OJ L 40, 11.2.1989, p. 34)

³ Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 of 15 November 2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs (OJ L 338, 22.12.2005, p. 1)

⁴ https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/ce8efc9d-8750-4b75-9563-7427da889666_en

⁵ Point 3(a)(iv)(1) of the Annex to Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2024/1141 of 14 December 2023 amending Annexes II and III to Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards specific hygiene requirements for certain meat, fishery products, dairy products and eggs (OJ L, 2024/1141, 19.4.2024, ELI: http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg_del/2024/1141/oj)

Terms of Reference (ToR)

In accordance with Art. 29 of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 the Commission asks EFSA to deliver a scientific opinion on the microbiological safety for the consumer (presence and growth of pathogens and spoilage bacteria after defrosting) by the freezing of fresh meat of ungulates (at least of domestic bovine, ovine, caprine, porcine and equine animals, and of wild boars and deers, if sufficient information is available) but excluding offals as defined in Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 853/2004.

For the purpose of the following assessment:

- Steps considered in the assessment: (i) Meat stabilisation of carcass/meat cuts to reach 7°C, (ii) refrigerated storage/transport of fresh carcass/meat cuts at 7°C before freezing (unless alternative temperature requested in the ToR),
- Stabilisation period is defined as the period needed for the carcass/meat cuts to reach a core temperature of 7°C and to stabilize the pH of meat by chilling applied immediately after slaughter (a matter of a few days, so shorter than a possible "maturation" period);
- The end point of this assessment would be the meat at the end of refrigeration and prior to freezing;
- The safety of the meat product at consumption will also be influenced by the storage conditions of the frozen meat, the thawing conditions, by the subsequent storage conditions, and by the possible further processing. Good hygiene practices during thawing should be assumed. Further steps after thawing at food business operator level are not under the scope of this mandate;
- Pathogenic as well as spoilage bacteria should be considered since also spoilage bacteria render the meat unfit for human consumption in accordance with Article 14(5) of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002.

More specifically, EFSA is asked:

TOR 1. To compare the effect on survival and growth of relevant food-borne pathogenic bacteria, indicator organisms and spoilage bacteria in fresh meat of ungulates that has been stored/transported at the following conditions applied between slaughter and freezing:

- core temperature of maximum 7°C until 15 days after slaughter;
- core temperature of maximum 7°C until 6 weeks after slaughter, vacuum-packed immediately after stabilisation;
- core temperature of maximum 3°C until 6 weeks after slaughter, vacuum-packed immediately after stabilisation.
- core temperature of maximum 7°C until 6 weeks after slaughter, vacuum-packed 15 days after slaughter;
- core temperature of maximum 3°C until 6 weeks after slaughter, vacuum-packed 15 days after slaughter.

TOR 2. If differences are identified in the survival and growth of relevant food-borne pathogenic or spoilage bacteria (outcome of ToR 1), then to

- identify refrigeration times/temperatures/use of vacuum packaging scenario's for meat intended to be frozen that would result in a similar load of the relevant bacterial hazards as compared to standard fresh (never frozen) meat; and,
- indicate which bacteria would be most relevant to monitor in these scenario's and what bacterial load might be expected just before freezing.

A.1.2.2 Request for a scientific opinion on the microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates: defrosting

- On 18 October 2024, the Commission submitted a mandate to EFSA requesting for a scientific opinion on the microbiological safety of meat of ungulates intended to be frozen. The mandate more specifically asked to deliver a scientific opinion on the microbiological safety for the consumer related to storage conditions before the freezing of fresh meat of ungulates.

The microbiological safety for the consumer will however also be influenced by the microbiological growth at and after defrosting of the meat. To allow risk managers to consider the need for additional control measures on frozen meat, an additional risk assessment should supplement the initial mandate by evaluating microbiological growth during defrosting and subsequent storage.

Current legal requirements related to frozen meat have been provided as background information in the initial mandate. Information provided by the industry on common practices of defrosting of meat of ungulates have been added to this mandate as an Appendix.

Terms of Reference (ToR)

In accordance with Art. 29 of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 the Commission asks EFSA to deliver a scientific opinion on the microbiological safety for the consumer (presence and growth of pathogens and spoilage bacteria) during defrosting and subsequent storage of meat of ungulates (at least of domestic bovine, ovine, caprine, porcine and equine animals, and of wild boars and deer, if sufficient information is available) but excluding offals as defined in Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 853/2004.

The baseline scenario for this assessment would be meat of ungulates that has been stored/transported at core temperature of maximum 7°C and for a maximum of 15 days after slaughter and prior to freezing.

The end point of this assessment would be the meat at the end of storage after defrosting. Further industrial processing and/or retail and consumer stages are excluded from this assessment for which good hygienic practices are assumed.

It can be assumed that no bacterial growth will occur during freezing. Different defrosting practices by consumer and at retail are outside the remit of this mandate.

More specifically, EFSA is asked:

TOR 1. To compare the effect on survival and growth of relevant food-borne pathogenic bacteria, indicator organisms and spoilage bacteria in defrosting scenarios where freezing occurs at -12 or -18 °C, defrosting at 4 or 7 °C, for short (4-8 h) or long (24-72 h) duration, dynamic or static defrosting applied, meat is vacuum-packed or not, and subsequent storage for 7 days at 4 or 7°C temperature.

TOR 2. Based on the outcome of the mandate on the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen and ToR 1 of this mandate, provide scenarios that consider the pre-freezing, defrosting and storage conditions that would result in a similar load of the relevant bacterial hazards as compared to standard fresh (never frozen) meat.

Indicate which bacteria would be most relevant to monitor in these scenarios and what bacterial load might be expected at the end of storage post defrosting.

A.1.3. Interpretation of the TORs of the mandate

The following has been clarified with the requestor:

- The first scenario described in ToR1, i.e. "core temperature of maximum 7°C until 15 days after slaughter" should be considered as the "reference scenario" equivalent to "standard fresh meat (never frozen) meat" for comparison purpose in ToR2. The relevant duration of this « reference scenario » can be tailored to the specific ungulate species as considered best until a maximum period of 15 days. For certain species (e.g., pork or ovine meat), a shorter duration than 15 days may be appropriate.
- The stabilisation period is defined as the period needed for the carcass/meat cuts to reach a core temperature of 7°C and to stabilize the pH of meat by chilling applied immediately after slaughter (a matter of a few days, so shorter than a possible "maturation" period). The surface temperature after stabilisation period is considered to be the same as the core temperature, i.e. 7°C.
- For ToR2, the WG defines thawing time as the period required for the complete disappearance of ice crystals at the core of the meat. This marks the end of the thawing phase. Bacterial growth on the surface is only considered up to this point.
- The assessment made in this opinion needs to include the stabilisation period, as the aim of the EC is to understand how long meat can be stored after slaughter and before freezing to decide how much flexibility can be allowed in the regulations to allow possibly longer storage periods before freezing. At the end of this stabilization period, depending on the scenario, the meat is either stored at 3°C or at 7°C. At this point, the surface temperature is assumed to instantaneously adjust to the respective storage temperature.
- When considering wild boar and deer in the context of both mandates we should only focus on farmed wild ungulates slaughtered in a slaughterhouse, as temperature conditions for hunted game are more difficult to control and will therefore not be considered here.
- The assessment can focus only on the potential growth and survival of bacterial microorganisms which is the group being relevant under the different scenario conditions to be evaluated. For scenario comparison with the reference, the growth of either relevant food-borne pathogenic or spoilage bacteria are considered. To establish a microbiological detection and/or quantification strategy, the growth of either hygiene indicator bacteria or spoilage bacteria are assessed.
- For pathogenic bacteria the predicted log₁₀ increase will be used as a measure of the bacterial growth whereas for spoilage and indicator bacteria initial loads together with log₁₀ increase will be assessed.
- In the assessment ungulates meat is used to refer both to ungulates carcasses and meat cuts.

A.2. Problem formulation

Step 1 consists of the translation of the mandate into assessment questions (AQs) and their relationship (conceptual model).

A.2.1. Assessment question(s) and conceptual model

The ToR1 of the mandate on the **microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates intended to be frozen** was translated into **5** assessment questions (AQs).

AQ.1.1.1 Which are the relevant bacteria and their levels to be considered in ungulates meat?

AQ.1.1.2 Which are the representative surface and core temperature profiles for each ungulate species during the initial carcass cooling phase/stabilisation period?

AQ.1.1.3 Which are the relevant intrinsic and extrinsic factors (excluding temperature) and their values for assessing bacterial growth during the storage/transport conditions?

AQ.1.1.4 Which are the existing predictive microbiology models appropriate for assessing the growth of relevant bacteria (AQ1.1) under the conditions defined in AQ.1.2 and AQ.1.3?

AQ.1.1.5 Are the tested scenarios different in terms of potential growth and survival of relevant bacteria based on defined equivalence criteria (outcome of ToR 1) ?

The ToR2 of the mandate on the **microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates intended to be frozen** was translated into **3** assessment questions (AQs).

AQ.1.2.1 Which are the storage/transport times for scenarios (temperatures/use of vacuum packaging) of ungulate meat intended to be frozen that would result in a similar load of pathogenic and spoilage bacteria as compared to standard fresh (never frozen) meat?

AQ.1.2.2 Which are the criteria to identify relevant bacteria to detect and/or quantify in these scenarios?

AQ.1.2.3 Which are the relevant bacteria to detect and/or quantify and the expected loads just before freezing?

The ToR1 of the mandate on the **microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates: defrosting** was translated into **2** assessment questions (AQs).

AQ.2.1.1 What are the representative surface temperature and core temperature profiles on meat of each ungulate species under the conditions to be evaluated during thawing?

AQ.2.1.2 What is the potential growth of relevant (AQ.1.1) bacteria at the ungulate meat surface temperature during thawing according to the AQ.2.1.1?

The ToR2 of the mandate on the **microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates: defrosting** was translated into **1** assessment question (AQ).

AQ2.2.1 Which are the equivalence thresholds obtained in AQ.1.2.1 that ensure similarity to the reference scenario taking also in consideration the thawing of ungulates meat?

The AQs and their relationship is shown through the conceptual model shown in Figure A.1.

The approach for each AQ, i.e., whether to apply a quantitative, qualitative or semi-quantitative approach, has been specified in Table A.1. There was no need to prioritise AQs.

Figure A.1: The relationship between the assessment questions (AQs). AQs from the mandate on the 'microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen' are shown in pink boxes and AQs from the mandate on the 'microbiological safety of defrosting of frozen meat of ungulates' are shown in blue boxes.

A.3. Methods that will be applied for conducting the assessment.

The second step includes the overall approach, as well as the evidence needs and the methods for answering each AQ including uncertainty analysis (i.e., the use of a literature review, data from databases, expert judgement and/or primary data collection). Table A.1 provides this information in the fifth (step 2.1a) and sixth (step 2.1b) columns.

The methods that will be used for evidence integration across AQs and for accounting for the remaining uncertainty are provided in Table A.2 based on the conceptual model.

Part 1 mandate: request for a scientific opinion on the microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates intended to be frozen

Table A.1. Assessment questions for the assessment of the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen (TOR 1.1.)

TOR 1.1 To compare the effect on survival and growth of relevant food-borne pathogenic bacteria, indicator organisms and spoilage bacteria in fresh meat of ungulates that has been stored/transported at the following conditions applied between slaughter and freezing:

- core temperature of maximum 7°C until 15 days after slaughter;
- core temperature of maximum 7°C until, 6 weeks after slaughter, vacuum-packed immediately after stabilisation;
- core temperature of maximum 3°C until 6 weeks after slaughter, vacuum-packed immediately after stabilisation.
- core temperature of maximum 7°C until, 6 weeks after slaughter, vacuum-packed 15 days after slaughter;
- core temperature of maximum 3°C until 6 weeks after slaughter, vacuum-packed 15 days after slaughter.

Step 1.1. Assessment questions (AQ)	Step 1.3. Overall approach	Step 2.1(a) Evidence needs	Step 2.1(b) Description of method to be used
AQ 1.1.1. Which are the relevant bacteria and their levels to be considered in ungulates meat?	Qualitative	Data from previous EFSA opinions and literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define which are the: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - main foodborne pathogens in ungulates meat (e.g. <i>Salmonella</i> spp., <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>, STEC, <i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i>) - indicator bacteria usually considered for ungulates meat (<i>E. coli</i>, Enterobacteriaceae, aerobic colony counts) - main spoilage bacteria (<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp., <i>Brochothrix thermosphacta</i>, <i>Lactobacillus</i> spp.,...) - as well as the association of relevant bacteria to each type of ungulates meat. • Identify initial contamination levels on carcasses before cooling based on observed data and/or values of microbiological criteria (m, M) for indicator bacteria (Enterobacteriaceae, aerobic colony counts), spoilage microorganisms and bacterial pathogens. • Using evidence from the relevant past EFSA opinions, literature selected by WG members as well as expert knowledge informally collected, as there is no need for an extensive literature search. • Possible sources of uncertainty will be captured in the 'uncertainty table' including impact of the uncertainty on the conclusions. If any uncertainty is found the methods used for uncertainty analysis will be qualitative.
AQ 1.1.2. Which are the representative surface and core temperature profiles for each ungulate species during the	Quantitative	Data from previous EFSA opinions and literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using evidence from the relevant past EFSA opinions, literature selected by WG members as well as expert knowledge informally collected (as there is no need for an extensive literature search) to identify relevant input data to model the initial ungulates meat cooling phase (including the stabilization period): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of data and/or models on cooling kinetics after slaughter for each ungulate,

<p>initial carcass cooling phase/stabilisation period?</p>			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of a standardized temperature profile (e.g., cooling to a core temperature within a given time) for the average and the worst-case scenarios of meat under different storage conditions. • Possible sources of uncertainty will be captured in the 'uncertainty table' including impact of the uncertainty on the conclusions. If any uncertainty is found the methods used for uncertainty analysis will be qualitative.
<p>AQ 1.1.3. Which are the relevant intrinsic and extrinsic factors (excluding temperature) and their values for assessing bacterial growth during the storage/transport conditions?</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Data from previous EFSA opinions and literature</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining of the intrinsic and extrinsic factors that impact the growth of bacteria on meat during storage (pH, aw, lactate, CO2...) • Determine the values of relevant intrinsic and extrinsic factors for each ungulate meats
<p>AQ 1.1.4. Which are the existing predictive microbiology models appropriate for assessing the growth of relevant bacteria (AQ1.1) under the conditions defined in AQ.1.2 and AQ.1.3?</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Data from previous EFSA opinions and literature</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using evidence from the relevant past EFSA opinions, literature selected by WG members as well as expert knowledge informally collected, as there is no need for an extensive literature search. • Identification of existing predictive models for bacterial pathogens, microbial indicators, and spoilage bacteria that account for relevant factors identified in AQ 1.2 and AQ1.3 in order to identify the relevant models to assess growth and survival for each bacteria type. The need of calibration factors will be considered. • Comparison of available and calibrated models (predicted growth kinetics relative to the reference temperature scenarios according to available models). • Relevant models will be selected for each bacteria type, prioritizing those used in previous related EFSA opinions to ensure consistency across assessments. Simulations with the selected predictive models will be relevant to compare the different scenarios but these cannot be considered as perfectly representative of absolute real levels of microorganisms. • Possible sources of uncertainty will be captured in the 'uncertainty table' including impact of the uncertainty on the conclusions. If any uncertainty is found the methods used for uncertainty analysis will be qualitative.
<p>AQ 1.1.5. Are the tested scenarios different in terms of potential growth and survival of relevant bacteria based on defined equivalence criteria (outcome of ToR 1)?</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Output from models</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparison of predicted microbial growth for each scenario vs. Reference (4 days until 15 days)

Table A.2. Assessment questions for the assessment of the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen (TOR 1.2)

TOR 1.2. If differences are identified in the survival and growth of relevant food-borne pathogenic or spoilage bacteria (outcome of ToR 1), then to

- identify refrigeration times/temperatures/use of vacuum packaging scenario's for meat intended to be frozen that would result in a similar load of the relevant bacterial hazards as compared to standard fresh (never frozen) meat; and,
- indicate which bacteria would be most relevant to monitor in these scenario's and what bacterial load might be expected just before freezing.

Step 1.1. Assessment questions (AQ)	Step 1.3. Overall approach	Step 2.1(a) Evidence needs	Step 2.1(b) Description of method to be used
AQ 1.2.1. Which are the storage/transport times for scenarios (temperatures/use of vacuum packaging) of ungulate meat intended to be frozen that would result in a similar load of pathogenic and spoilage bacteria as compared to standard fresh (never frozen) meat?	Quantitative	Output from the models	<p>Criterion for definition of the equivalence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of an equivalence criterion for comparison (e.g., a difference ≤ 0.3 log between predicted levels for reference and a scenario is considered equivalent, "exact match" with reference, last day before being above reference). <p>Storage time for the scenarios Based on the predicted growth of pathogens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calculate equivalent storage/transport times for each bacteria according to equivalence criteria defined in AQ 1.4 that gives similarity with the reference scenario. • Identification of the limiting storage/transport times
AQ 1.2.2. Which are the criteria to identify relevant bacteria to detect and/or quantify in these scenarios?	Qualitative	Data from previous EFSA opinions and literature	The working group will propose some criteria to identify which bacteria should be detected and/or quantified for assessing the growth of bacteria prior to freezing.
AQ 1.2.3. Which are the relevant bacteria to detect and/or quantify and the	Qualitative and semi-quantitative	Output from models	The working group will identify one or several bacteria that could be detected and/or quantified for each ungulate meat based on the defined criteria. Some indications of the expected levels on meats just before thawing according to different initial contaminations will be provided.

expected loads just before freezing?			
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Part 2 mandate: request for a scientific opinion on the microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates: defrosting

Table A.3. Assessment questions for the assessment of the microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates: defrosting (TOR 2.1.)

TOR 2.1. To compare the effect on survival and growth of relevant food-borne pathogenic bacteria, indicator organisms and spoilage bacteria in defrosting scenarios where freezing occurs at -12 or -18 °C, defrosting at 4 or 7 °C, for short (4-8 h) or long (24-72 h) duration, dynamic or static defrosting applied, meat is vacuum-packed or not, and subsequent storage for 7 days at 4 or 7°C temperature

Step 1.1. Assessment questions (AQ)	Step 1.3. Overall approach	Step 2.1(a) Evidence needs	Step 2.1(b) Description of method to be used
AQ 2.1.1. What are the representative surface temperature and core temperature profiles on meat of each ungulate species under the conditions to be evaluated during thawing?	Qualitative	Data and model from scientific literature and industry data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using evidence from the scientific literature selected by WG members as well as expert knowledge informally collected, as there is no need for an extensive literature search, identify: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> pieces of ungulates meat to be considered (e.g. worst case with largest piece of meat and/or corresponding to primal cuts, deboned meat...) data and models for surface temperature of ungulates meat available during thawing according to chosen meat piece(s). Possible sources of uncertainty will be captured in the 'uncertainty table' including impact of the uncertainty on the conclusions. If any uncertainty is found the methods used for uncertainty analysis will be qualitative.
AQ 2.1.2. What is the potential growth of relevant (AQ.1.1) bacteria at the ungulate meat surface temperature during thawing according to the AQ.2.1.1?	Quantitative	Output from models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using evidence TORs from part I, literature selected by WG members as well as expert knowledge informally collected, as there is no need for an extensive literature search. For the same pairs of bacteria/meat assess the growth on surface during thawing for each pair of bacteria/meat type. Possible sources of uncertainty will be captured in the 'uncertainty table' including impact of the uncertainty on the conclusions. If any uncertainty is found the methods used for uncertainty analysis will be qualitative.

Table A.4. Assessment questions for the assessment of the microbiological safety of frozen meat of ungulates: defrosting (TOR 2.2.)

TOR 2.2. Based on the outcome of the mandate on the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen and ToR 1 of this mandate, provide scenarios that consider the pre-freezing, defrosting and storage conditions that would result in a similar load of the relevant bacterial hazards as compared to standard fresh (never frozen) meat.

Indicate which bacteria would be most relevant to monitor in these scenarios and what bacterial load might be expected at the end of storage post defrosting.

Step 1.1. Assessment questions (AQ)	Step 1.3. Overall approach	Step 2.1(a) Evidence needs	Step 2.1(b) Description of method to be used
AQ 2.2.1. Which are the equivalence thresholds obtained in AQ.1.2.1 that ensure similarity to the reference scenario taking also in consideration the thawing of ungulates meat?	Quantitative	Output from models developed by the working group	The limiting storage/transport times established in AQ 1.6 will be adjusted according to the growth observed during thawing.

Table A.5. Integration of evidence across sub-questions and remaining overall uncertainty

TOR/AQ	Step 2.2. Integration of evidence between AQs	Step 2.2. Addressing overall uncertainty
TOR 1.1.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The AQ 1.1.1., 1.1.2., 1.1.3., 1.1.4. and 1.1.5. each address part of TOR 1.1. Combined they address the ToR 1.1. • Evidence integration across AQs is not needed as the AQs are organised in a logical sequence that requires the answer to the first AQ to feed into the next, until the TOR 1.1. is answered. 	There is no need to plan beforehand.
TOR 1.2.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The AQ 1.2.1., 1.2.2. and 1.2.3. collectively address TOR 1.2. The evidence gathered from AQ 1.2.1. to 1.2.3. will be integrated to comprehensively address ToR 1.2. • AQ1.1.5 will help to check if application of other AQ are necessary. • Evidence integration with AQ 1.2.1. is quantitative (permitting to merge data for TOR1.1 in growth potential for pathogens). • AQ 1.2.2. and 1.2.3. will provide qualitative and semi-quantitative information in order to help the risk manager to potentially establish some way to monitor proper cold chain management of ungulates meat before thawing. 	There is no need to plan beforehand.
TOR 2.1.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The AQ 2.1.1 and AQ 2.1.2. collectively address TOR 2.1. The evidence from AQ 2.1.1 (qualitative) and AQ 2.1.2 (quantitative) will be integrated to comprehensively address ToR 2.1. • Evidence integration across these AQs will involve identifying relevant data on surface temperature during thawing (AQ 2.1.1) and combining it with microbial growth model predictions (AQ 2.1.2) for different pairs of bacteria and ungulate meat types. • Uncertainties identified in these AQs will be captured qualitatively in an uncertainty table, including their potential impact on overall conclusions. 	There is no need to plan beforehand.
TOR 2.2.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AQ 2.2.1 is helping to relate part 1 and part 2 of the mandate. It will allow to quantitatively link the impact of both the pre-freezing and the thawing conditions. 	There is no need to plan beforehand.

AQ = assessment question

A.4. Amendments to the protocol

A few minor amendments to the approved protocol took place once the implementation phase and assessments had already started. Table A.6 describes all modifications to the protocol providing a justification for each modification as well as the date of agreement for each modification.

Number	Date	Section of the protocol	Protocol amendment
1	3 June 2025	A.1.3 – Interpretation of terms of reference	During the assessment, in consultation with the mandate requestor, and considering the data available, it was decided to focus the assessment on meat from bovine, ovine and porcine animals, while excluding caprine, equine and farmed/slaughtered wild boar and deer, for which possible extrapolation from the above species was considered, when possible, based on available data.

2	18 August 2025	A.3, Table A.1, AQ 1.1.1 – Methods that will be applied for conducting the assessment	With regards to spoilage bacteria and indicator microorganisms, it was decided to define different example scenarios for initial contamination levels. Such initial contamination levels: i) were selected to be in line with levels reported in scientific literature and microbiological criteria; ii) were considered at post-chilling level instead of pre-chilling level, to be compatible with information retrieved from scientific literature.
3	18 August 2025	A.1.3 – Interpretation of terms of reference	Considering practical conditions during defrosting to avoid cross-contamination and the possible presence of foreign bodies originating from packaging material, it was assumed, in agreement with the mandate requestor, that vacuum packed meat is always defrosted inside their vacuum package and unpacked only at the end of defrosting.

References

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